

Malabar Nut *Adhatoda Vasica* Linn. Cultivation Practices and Domestication for *Ex-situ* Conservation

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Abstract

Since the Covid-19 everyone has been relied on the herbs for health care. All over the world as well as in India many plants were scrutinized for anti-cough, respiratory diseases, cold and thought infection. Many plants like *Adhatoda vasica*, *Barlaria sp.*, *Tinospora sp.*, *Gingiber sp.*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Piper sp.* etc. were recommended by Ministry of AUSH, Govt. of India. *Adhatoda vasica* is the important plant of bronchial diseases. It is dominated in the pollution free waste land area of the world. The plant is wildly grown but it is required to introduced in the agro-practices also for fulfillment of constant demand & supply. It may be cultured either by seed germination or by grafting method. The seed germination is taken palace at 16⁰C (61⁰F) in spring and rainy season . The well-drained soil, waste land partial shade with high humidity is favorable for the perfect germination of seeds. The grafting method was also successful during rainy season. cow urine is good promotor of roots in the grafting. A bushy shrub plant was developed in the matured form. The *Adhatoda vasica* was used for many diseases. The plant was highly exploited by herbal Pharmacies therefore the herb is depleting from the natural homes.

Keywords

Malabar Nut, Adhatoda, Vasica, Linn. Cultivation, Ex-situ Conservation.

Introduction

The medicinal plants play a vital role in providing medical aids to ailing people, promoting health to mankind since time immemorial. The use of medicinal plants is well-mentioned in Indian Systems of Medicine and Homoeopathy. Still there are a number of such plants which need to be domesticated, vasica being an excellent example. (Kashyap et al 2002)

Vasica is distributed all over the plains of India and in the lower Himalayan ranges, up to the height of 1,500 m above mean sea-level. It is abundant in tropical Africa, China, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, Burma, Bangladesh and Pakistan. Its life-span is 2-3 years or more. It shows variation in chromosome numbers, viz. 34, 40, 46 and 50 or 56. (Kumar et al 2023)

Objective of study

1. To identify the area of distribution of Adhatoda vasica.
2. To find out the parameters of domestication and agriculture practices for sustainable growth.
3. To find out the different component utilized in the different ailment of the human beings.

Review of Literature

The present study is supported by different eminent workers as the flora of the Delhi NCR region was also studied time to time by the Botanist and gives the great information of the crude drug and its active constituents like vasicine and vasicinone (Bhide, et al, 1976). Wakhloo et al 1979 studied on interruption of pregnancy by vasicine. Atal (1980) studied of the vasicine *Chemistry and pharmacology*. Rajani and Bhavsar (1994) did the work on the role of vasicine with chloramphenicol in *Datura innoxia* Mill. Rajani and Pundari kakshudu (1996) studied on the seasonal variation of alkaloids in *Adhatoda*

vasica Nees. Sharma (1996) wrote a book on *Classical uses of medicinal plants*. CCRAS Report 2000 showed the plant in its *Database on Medicinal Plants used in Ayurveda*. Niranjan et al (2002) Give the method of estimation of alkaloid by spectrophotometric in the stem bark and seed. Verma and Lal (2014) did the work on Ayurvedic medicines and Natural Remedy by Punarnava. Bhowmik D, Sampath KP, Srivastava S, Paswan S, Dutta AS. Goraya and Ved (2017) did the work on the assessment of demand and supply of the medicinal plants with the help of concerned agencies similarly Samal (2016) surveyed on the Medicinal plants and related developments in India on the basis of Five year Plans survey. Ashrafi et al (2022) studied on the current years Asian plants prospective with their corroborated antiviral potentials. Kashyap (2002) did the Comparative studies on habitat and storage specificity for certain medicinal plants during his research work in Ph.D Kashyap et al (2007) worked on the storage specificity for *Adhatoda zeylanicamedicus* as a crude drug and find some correlated results. Kumar et al (2023) worked on the Phytogeographical Distribution of *Adhatoda vasica L.* in NCR Delhi Region. Kashyap et al (2002) .did the work on the domesticating bhrangraj and raktapunarnava for ex situ conservation and agro practices.

Hypothesis

The present study will be based on the Agricultural practices of *Adhatoda vasica* in Delhi NCR Region. Pharmacognostical and agronomical studies are based on the wild and agricultural trial practices. We can conserve the plant species by agricultural practices. The ex-situ and in-situ conservation is needed for sustainable development. The stressed and unstressed areas showed the different habitats varied the quality & efficacy. The investigation areas of the plant species are under geographical distribution maps and BSI reports.

Analysis

Economical Importance:

Its plants are obtained as wild 2000, about 4211.9 tons of plant bio mass was required which may go up to 1,065.4 tons in 2004-05. The market prices vary from Rs 58 to 70 (Cochin and Trichur), Rs 60 (Dehradun), Rs 65 (Delhi) and Rs 58 (Haridwar)/kg. The average growth rate of demand is 10.9%/annum.

Aayurvedic Importance:

Its temperament (tasir) is hot and dry in the first degree. It is bitter as- stringent, antispasmodic, antiseptic, alleviative, blood purifier, tonic and expectorant. *Vasica* is used in liver enlargement, hepatitis, jaundice and vomiting. The drug *Vasaca* or *Adusa* have used in the indigenous system of medicine for a long time. It is beneficial for heart and throat. The roots are useful for the treatment of gonorrhoea. They are more extensively used in chronic and acute bronchitis, cough, asthma and bronchiodilatory activity due to the presence of vaccine and vasicinone. It was widely used in preparing cough syrups. The juice of fresh leaves is used for, diarrhoea, dysentery, antiperiodic, antiseptic and anthelmintic. Leaves and flowers are efficacious against rheumatic painful swelling and other skin diseases.(Verma and Lal, 2014)

Plant's Potential Values:

A number of pharmaceutical manufacturing concerns and classical preparations are made by *vasica*. Some examples are: Ashokarishta, Kumary-asava, *Vasaka-asava*, *Vasa-Pancharista*, Guggulu, dasamool, *Vasavaleha*, *Vasasvarasa*, *Vasaghrita* etc. An alcoholic extract of its dried leaves has strong local anesthetic property. It inhibits salivary secretion induced by pilocarpine. Vasinine, bronchiodilatory stimulant, slightly hypotensive, uterine stimulant and abortifacient activity similar to that of oxytocin and methergin. Uterine stimulant action was seen on human myometrium. The uterotonic and abortifacient active. It may be used during pregnancy for abortive. Its antiseptic and spermocidal character is essential oil present in leaves. *Vasica* is highly active against amlapitta, pyorrhoea, local bleeding and gums (teeth). The fresh leaves juice generally used in tuberculosis. It cures in vomiting, thirst, fever, neuralgia, dermatitis, tonsils, throat soar diphtheria, peptid ulcer & piles. It is also used in Rhinitis means loss of taste and smell due to swollen of nose, throat, mouth and tongue and all feel dry.

The Research Area :

The proposed study research area is the Delhi NCR Region which has the major Geographical areas included agricultural region of NCT Delhi, Ghaziabad, Baghpat, Meerut, Hapur, Bulandshar and some areas of Haryana from North latitude 28⁰44'42"N and East longitude 77⁰05'35"E. This is highly developing area in the urbanization. It is depleting the herbal plants from the list of dominating medicinal plants. The samples and the survey was also done near the unstressed areas like hill stations which are free from transportation and industries. The *adhatoda vasica* plants were luxuriantly found in the

hill areas and waste lands of rural areas which were not affected from pollutions. (Gorava & Ved 2017)

Crude Drugs Resources :

However the vasaka plants are obtained in wild 2000 at to 4211.9 tons of plant biomass was required which may go up to 1,065.4 tons in 2004-05. The market prices vary from Rs 58 to 70 (Cochin and Trichur), Rs 60 (Dehradun), Rs 65 (Delhi) and Rs 58 (Haridwar)/kg. The average growth rate of demand is 10.9% / annum. (Kashyap et al 2005, 2006 and 2007)

Domesticating Parameters :

Vasaka (*Adhatoda zeylanica* Medicus) is a native plant of India, belonging to family Acanthaceae. It is an evergreen perennial shrub of 250- 450 cm height, with much branched woody stem. The leaves are green, simple, lanceolate, reticulate veination. Inflorescence is axillary raceme spikelet with zygomorphic flowers. Seed germination is taken place at 16⁰C (61⁰ F) in spring. Well drained Soil, waste land partial shade with high humidity was favaourable for the perfect germination of seeds. The grafting method was also successful during rainy season. A bushy Shrub plant is developed in the mature form. The experiment was set during the germination practice; the cow urine had been taken for fast rooting. On stem cutting of the hard and soft part were used for grafting culture.

The flowering of plants was observed during February to May and September to November. Temperature 30⁰C is more suitable for luxuriant flowering and fruiting. It can be grown by grafting, vegetative propagation and seed propagation. During the rainy season the seeds are naturally germinated but in the field it could be shown during October November or in February April. Vegetaive propagation was found developed during any season except cold winters. The seed dispersal was very interested that is gun bullet dehiscence. (Kashyap et al 2007)

Result and Discussion

The experiment was conducted at Botany Department, M.M.(PG) College, Modinagar Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh. The prime objective of its evaluation was to know its economic viability for sustainable development under domestic cultivation. The observations were taken under natural as well as domesticated conditions. It could be cultivated in wastelands, bank of rivers, canals, and drainage or around fields. Its seeds can be collected during blossom periods which come twice in a year viz. November-December and March-April. The seeds are dispersed by explosive

mechanism. The seeds are smaller to lens bean (musoor) and non-endospermic. The seeds are mixed with soil at 60-80% humid soil at pH 7-8 to grow. The optimum temperature for its proper growth is $32^{\circ} \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and good light. The seeds germinate in 10-15 days. The plant matured in 70-90 days. In natural conditions, it germinated during rainy season (July-September) but it can be grown during February-March commercially. There is no need to do hard work in its crop-ping. It can be harvested 2-3 times or more from a single cropping. It grows to a height of 250-400 cm in a year. The flowering takes place in 90-120 days. Its biomass could be obtained. The seedlings were transplanted in the field successfully. The sewage effluent is more suitable than pure water. It some times flourishes vigorously nearby vehicular pollution, polluted water and wastelands. Therefore, it may be planted at polluted areas as pollution absorbent plant.

Conclusion

Vasica is under exploited medicinal plant in market & demand for immense utility. Since it is used in the preparation of a number of drugs. Its domestication is the need of the day. Vasica had been using since ancient time. At present, the plant is exploited therefore it required to conserve and ex-situ or in-situ conservation. Sometimes adulteration was seen in the herb in replace to *Ailanthus excelsa* leaves.

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